

Appendix: Identifiers of the Reviewed Articles

Each article included in the systematic review was given a unique identifier. This was to facilitate the visualization of the data in the figures of the manuscript. The identifiers and the corresponding full references are listed below:

- AA14 → Achemoukh, F., & Ahmed-Ouamer, R. (2014). Representation and evolution of user profile in information retrieval based on Bayesian approach. *Proceedings of the 21st International Symposium on Methodologies for Intelligent Systems (ISMIS)*, 486–492. <https://doi.org/10.1109/isko-maghreb.2013.6728112>
- Afc+22 → Afchar, D., Melchiorre, A., Schedl, M., Hennequin, R., Epure, E., et al. (2022). Explainability in music recommender systems. *AI Magazine*, 43(2), 190–208. <https://doi.org/10.1002/aaai.12056>
- AHX13 → Abdel-Hafez, A., & Xu, Y. (2013). A survey of user modelling in social media websites. *Computer and Information Science*, 6(4), 59–71. <https://doi.org/10.5539/cis.v6n4p59>
- AION15 → Amini, B., Ibrahim, R., Othman, M. S., & Nematbakhsh, M. A. (2015). A reference ontology for profiling scholar’s background knowledge in recommender systems. *Expert Systems with Applications*, 42(2), 913–928. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eswa.2014.08.031>
- Aiv+19 → Aivazoglou, M., Roussos, A. O., Margaris, D., Vassilakis, C., Ioannidis, S., et al. (2019). A fine-grained social network recommender system. *Social Network Analysis and Mining*, 10(1), 1–18, article no.: 8. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13278-019-0621-7>
- Amm+19 → Ammad-ud-din, M., Ivannikova, E., Khan, S. A., Oyomno, W., Fu, Q., et al. (2019). Federated collaborative filtering for privacy-preserving personalized recommendation system
- AS99 → Amato, G., & Straccia, U. (1999). User profile modeling and applications to digital libraries. *Proceedings of the 3rd International Conference on Theory and Practice of Digital Libraries (TPDL)*, 184–197. https://doi.org/10.1007/3-540-48155-9_13
- AT05 → Adomavicius, G., & Tuzhilin, A. (2005). Toward the next generation of recommender systems: A survey of the state-of-the-art and possible extensions. *IEEE Transactions on Knowledge and Data Engineering*, 17(6), 734–749. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TKDE.2005.99>
- BBC+08 → Boldi, P., Bonchi, F., Castillo, C., Donato, D., Gionis, A., et al. (2008). The query-flow graph: Model and applications. *Proceedings of the 17th ACM Conference on Information and Knowledge Management (CIKM)*, 609–618. <https://doi.org/10.1145/1458082.1458163>
- BHBTC22 → Ben Hassen, A., Ben Ticha, S., & Chaibi, A. H. (2022). Deep learning for visual-features extraction based personalized user modeling. *SN Computer Science*, 3(4), 1–13, article no.: 261. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42979-022-01131-y>
- BKN07 → Brusilovski, P., Kobsa, A., & Nejdil, W. (2007). User models for adaptive hypermedia and adaptive educational systems. In *The adaptive web: Methods and strategies*

of web personalization (pp. 3–53, Vol. 4321). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-540-72079-9_1

- BKR07 → Berkovsky, S., Kuflik, T., & Ricci, F. (2007). Cross-domain mediation in collaborative filtering. *Proceedings of the 11th International Conference on User Modeling (UM)*, 355–359. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-540-73078-1_44
- BOHG13 → Bobadilla, J., Ortega, F., Hernando, A., & Gutiérrez, A. (2013). Recommender systems survey. *Knowledge-Based Systems*, 46, 109–132. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.knosys.2013.03.012>
- Bro 16 → Browne, D. (1990). *Adaptive user interfaces*. Academic Press
- BWC+12 → Bennett, P. N., White, R. W., Chu, W., Dumais, S. T., Bailey, P., et al. (2012). Modeling the impact of short-and long-term behavior on search personalization. *Proceedings of the 35th International ACM SIGIR Conference on Research and Development in Information Retrieval (ICTIR)*, 185–194. <https://doi.org/10.1145/2348283.2348312>
- CC12 → Codina, V., & Ceccaroni, L. (2012). Semantically-enhanced recommenders. In *Artificial intelligence research and development* (pp. 69–78, Vol. 248). IOS Press. <https://doi.org/10.3233/978-1-61499-139-7-69>
- CCD+19 → Chanson, A., Crulis, B., Drushku, K., Labroche, N., et al. (2019). Profiling user belief in BI exploration for measuring subjective interestingness. *Proceedings of the 2019 International Conference on Extending Database Technology and International Conference on Database Theory (EDBT/ICDT)*
- CFV+08 → Cantador, I., Fernández, M., Vallet, D., Castells, P., et al. (2008). A multi-purpose ontology-based approach for personalized content filtering and retrieval. In *Advances in semantic media adaptation and personalization* (pp. 25–51). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-540-76361_2
- Cha+21 → Chang, W., Zhang, Q., Fu, C., Liu, W., Zhang, G., et al. (2021). A cross-domain recommender system through information transfer for medical diagnosis. *Decision Support Systems*, 143, 1–16, article no.: 113489. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dss.2020.113489>
- CKL15 → Chen, L.-C., Kuo, P.-J., & Liao, I.-E. (2015). Ontology-based library recommender system using MapReduce. *Cluster Computing*, 18(1), 113–121. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10586-013-0342-z>
- CL24 → Chen, Y.-C., & Lee, W.-C. (2024). A novel cross-domain recommendation with evolution learning. *ACM Trans. Internet Technol.*, 24(1). <https://doi.org/10.1145/3639567>
- CLHW24 → Chen, J., Liu, Z., Huang, X., Wu, C., Liu, Q., et al. (2024). When large language models meet personalization: Perspectives of challenges and opportunities. *World Wide Web*, 27(4), 1–45, article no.: 42. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11280-024-01276-1>
- CLS+21 → Chen, H., Li, Y., Sun, X., Xu, G., & Yin, H. (2021). Temporal meta-path guided explainable recommendation. *Proceedings of the 14th ACM International Conference on Web Search and Data Mining (WSDM)*, 1056–1064. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3437963.3441762>
- CMVGRG+15 → Colombo-Mendoza, L. O., Valencia-García, R., Rodríguez-González,

- A., Alor-Hernández, G., & Samper-Zapater, J. J. (2015). RecomMetz: A context-aware knowledge-based mobile recommender system for movie showtimes. *Expert Systems with Applications*, 42(3), 1202–1222. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eswa.2014.09.016>
- CP09 → Chu, W., & Park, S.-T. (2009). Personalized recommendation on dynamic content using predictive bilinear models. *Proceedings of the 18th International Conference on World Wide Web (WWW)*, 691–700. <https://doi.org/10.1145/1526709.1526802>
 - dPCS13 → de Paiva, F. A. P., Costa, J. A. F., & Silva, C. R. M. (2013). A hierarchical architecture for ontology-based recommender systems. *Proceedings of the 2013 BRICS Congress on Computational Intelligence and 11st Brazilian Congress on Computational Intelligence (BRICS-CCI & CBIC)*, 362–367. <https://doi.org/10.1109/brics-cci-cbic.2013.67>
 - DSRO20 → Da’u, A., Salim, N., Rabiou, I., & Osman, A. (2020). Weighted aspect-based opinion mining using deep learning for recommender system. *Expert Systems with Applications*, 140, 1–12, article no.: 112871. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eswa.2019.112871>
 - DZD22 → Deng, C., Zhou, Y., & Dou, Z. (2022). Improving personalized search with dual-feedback network. *Proceedings of the 15th ACM International Conference on Web Search and Data Mining (WSDM)*, 210–218. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3488560.3498447>
 - EHNA19 → El Houda, B. N., Nadjia, B., & Abdelkrim, M. (2019). Queries-based profile evolution using genetic algorithm. *Proceedings of the 16th IEEE/ACS International Conference on Computer Systems and Applications (AICCSA)*. <https://doi.org/10.1109/aiccsa47632.2019.9035351>
 - ENSN19 → Eke, C. I., Norman, A. A., Shuib, L., & Nweke, H. F. (2019). A survey of user profiling: State-of-the-art, challenges, and solutions. *IEEE Access*, 7, 144907–144924. <https://doi.org/10.1109/access.2019.2944243>
 - FEMR18 → Farid, M., Elgohary, R., Moawad, I., & Roushdy, M. (2018). User profiling approaches, modeling, and personalization. *Proceedings of the 11th International Conference on Informatics and Systems (INFOS)*. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3389811>
 - Fer+24 → Fermé, E., Garapa, M., Reis, M. D., Almeida, Y., Paulino, T., et al. (2024). Knowledge-driven profile dynamics. *Artificial Intelligence*, 331, 1–30, article no.: 104117. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.artint.2024.104117>
 - FFJZ06 → Felfernig, A., Friedrich, G., Jannach, D., & Zanker, M. (2006). An integrated environment for the development of knowledge-based recommender applications. *International Journal of Electronic Commerce*, 11(2), 11–34. <https://doi.org/10.1017/cbo9780511763113>
 - FL07 → Felden, C., & Linden, M. (2007). Ontology-based user profiling. *Proceedings of the 10th International Conference on Business Information Systems (BIS)*, 314–327. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-540-72035-5_24
 - FPW+19 → Fu, W., Peng, Z., Wang, S., Xu, Y., & Li, J. (2019). Deeply fusing reviews and contents for cold start users in cross-domain recommendation systems. *Proceedings of the 33rd AAAI Conference on Artificial Intelligence and 31st Innovative Applications of Artificial Intelligence Conference and 9th AAAI Symposium on Educational Advances in Artificial Intelligence*, 94–101. <https://doi.org/10.1609/aaai.v33i01.330194>

- FS06 → Fan, H., & Poole, M. S. (2006). What is personalization? perspectives on the design and implementation of personalization in information systems. *Journal of Organizational Computing and Electronic Commerce*, 16(3-4), 179–202. https://doi.org/10.1207/s15327744joce1603&4_2
- FTDCM18 → Farnadi, G., Tang, J., De Cock, M., & Moens, M.-F. (2018). User profiling through deep multimodal fusion. *Proceedings of the 11th ACM International Conference on Web Search and Data Mining (WSDM)*, 171–179. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3159652.3159691>
- Gen+22 → Geng, S., Liu, S., Fu, Z., Ge, Y., & Zhang, Y. (2022). Recommendation as language processing (RLP): A unified pretrain, personalized prompt & predict paradigm (P5). *Proceedings of the 16th ACM Conference on Recommender Systems*, 299–315. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3523227.3546767>
- GKVL+07 → Maria, G., Akrivi, K., Costas, V., George, L., & Constantin, H. (2007). Creating an ontology for the user profile: Method and applications. *Proceedings of the 1st International Conference on Research Challenges in Information Science (RCIS)*, 407–412. <https://doi.org/10.4018/9781605660325.ch009>
- GLH+21 → Gao, C., Lei, W., He, X., de Rijke, M., & Chua, T.-S. (2021). Advances and challenges in conversational recommender systems: A survey. *AI Open*, 2, 100–126. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aiopen.2021.06.002>
- GSCM07 → Gauch, S., Speretta, M., Chandramouli, A., & Micarelli, A. (2007). User profiles for personalized information access. In *The adaptive web: Methods and strategies of web personalization* (pp. 54–89, Vol. 4321). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-540-72079-9_2
- GWZH17 → Gao, L., Wu, J., Zhou, C., & Hu, Y. (2017). Collaborative dynamic sparse topic regression with user profile evolution for item recommendation. *Proceedings of the 31st Association for the Advancement of Artificial Intelligence Conference on Artificial Intelligence (AAAI)*, 31(1). <https://doi.org/10.1609/aaai.v31i1.10726>
- GXCM14 → Gao, Q., Xi, S. M., Cho, Y. I., & Matson, E. T. (2014). A multi-agent context-based personalized user preference profile construction approach. *Proceedings of the 14th International Symposium on Advanced Intelligent Systems (ISIS)*, 55–69. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-05573-2_6
- HF15 → Hawalah, A., & Fasli, M. (2015). Dynamic user profiles for web personalisation. *Expert Systems with Applications*, 42(5), 2547–2569. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eswa.2014.10.032>
- Hou+22 → Cao, J., Li, S., Yu, B., Guo, X., Liu, T., et al. (2023). Towards universal cross-domain recommendation. *Proceedings of the 16th ACM International Conference on Web Search and Data Mining*, 78–86. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3539597.3570366>
- HYKL03 → Hall, C. B., Ying, J., Kuo, L., & Lipton, R. B. (2003). Bayesian and profile likelihood change point methods for modeling cognitive function over time. *Computational Statistics & Data Analysis*, 42(1-2), 91–109. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0167-9473\(02\)00148-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0167-9473(02)00148-2)
- IFO15 → Isinkaye, F. O., Folajimi, Y. O., & Ojokoh, B. A. (2015). Recommendation

systems: Principles, methods and evaluation. *Egyptian Informatics Journal*, 16(3), 261–273. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eij.2015.06.005>

- JHC25 → Jiang, B., Hao, Z., Cho, Y.-M., Li, B., Yuan, Y., et al. (2025). Know me, respond to me: Benchmarking LLMs for dynamic user profiling and personalized responses at scale
- Kru97 → Krulwich, B. (1997). Lifestyle finder: Intelligent user profiling using large-scale demographic data. *AI Magazine*, 18(2), 37–37. <https://doi.org/10.1609/aimag.v18i2.1292>
- KSYF18 → Liu, S., Chen, Z., Liu, H., & Hu, X. (2018). AK tourism: A property graph ontology-based tourism recommender system. *Proceedings of the Knowledge Management International Conference (KMICe)*, 83–88
- KVRH23 → Kirk, H. R., Vidgen, B., Röttger, P., & Hale, S. A. (2023). Personalisation within bounds: A risk taxonomy and policy framework for the alignment of large language models with personalised feedback. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s42256-024-00820-y>
- La02 → Lau, R. Y. (2002). The state of the art in adaptive information agents. *International Journal on Artificial Intelligence Tools*, 11(1), 19–61. <https://doi.org/10.1142/S0218213002000770>
- Liu+23 → Liu, Q., Wu, J., Huang, Z., Wang, H., Ning, Y., et al. (2023). Federated user modeling from hierarchical information. *ACM Trans. Inf. Syst.*, 41(2). <https://doi.org/10.1145/3442381.3449926>
- LJZ08 → Liu, W., Jin, F., & Zhang, X. (2008). Ontology-based user modeling for e-commerce system. *Proceedings of the 3rd International Conference on Pervasive Computing and Applications (ICPCA)*, 1, 260–263. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICPCA.2008.4783589>
- LL09 → Leung, K. W.-T., & Lee, D. L. (2009). Deriving concept-based user profiles from search engine logs. *IEEE Transactions on Knowledge and Data Engineering*, 22(7), 969–982. <https://doi.org/10.1109/tkde.2009.144>
- LLY25 → Li, Y., Liu, Y., & Yu, M. (2025). Consumer segmentation with large language models. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 82, 1–13, article no.: 104078. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jretconser.2024.104078>
- LMNS19 → Lops, P., Musto, C., Narducci, F., & Semeraro, G. (2019). *Semantics in adaptive and personalised systems: Methods, tools and applications*. Springer. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-05618-6>
- LMR09 → López-Jaquero, V., Montero, F., & Real, F. (2009). Designing user interface adaptation rules with T: XML. *Proceedings of the 14th International Conference on Intelligent User Interfaces (IUI)*, 383–388. <https://doi.org/10.1145/1502650.1502705>
- LN12 → Lauschke, C., & Ntoutsi, E. (2012). Monitoring user evolution in Twitter. *Proceedings of the 2012 IEEE/ACM International Conference on Advances in Social Networks Analysis and Mining (ASONAM)*, 972–977
- LNN+10 → Le, D.-L., Nguyen, A.-T., Nguyen, D.-T., Tran, V.-H., & Hunger, A. (2010). A survey of applying user profile in the adaptive instructional systems. *Proceedings of the 5th International Conference on e-Learning (ICEL)*, 207–218. <https://doi.org/10.32508/>

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- LNNH09 → Le, D.-L., Nguyen, A.-T., Nguyen, D.-T., & Hunger, A. (2009). Building learner profile in adaptive e-learning systems. *Proceedings of the 4th International Conference on e-Learning (ICEL)*, 15–17. <https://doi.org/10.32508/stdj.v14i1.1881>
- LPL+16 → Lu, Z., Pan, S. J., Li, Y., Jiang, J., & Yang, Q. (2016). Collaborative evolution for user profiling in recommender systems. *Proceedings of the 25th International Joint Conference on Artificial Intelligence (IJCAI)*, 3804–3810. <https://doi.org/10.5555/3061053.3061151>
- LS12 → Lau, R. Y. K., & Song, L. (2012). Belief revision for intelligent web service recommendation. In *Computer and information science 2012* (pp. 53–66, Vol. 429). Springer
- LXS22 → Luo, S., Xiao, Y., & Song, L. (2022). Personalized federated recommendation via joint representation learning, user clustering, and model adaptation. *Proceedings of the 31st ACM International Conference on Information & Knowledge Management*, 4289–4293. <https://doi.org/10.1109/icipsp55539.2022.10050588>
- LYWK07 → Li, L., Yang, Z., Wang, B., & Kitsuregawa, M. (2007). Dynamic adaptation strategies for long-term and short-term user profile to personalize search. *Proceedings of the Joint 9th Asia-Pacific Web Conference (APWeb)*, 228–240. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-540-72524-4_26
- LZ20 → Li, S., & Zhao, H. (2020). A survey on representation learning for user modeling. *Proceedings of the 29th International Joint Conference on Artificial Intelligence, IJCAI-20*, 4997–5003. <https://doi.org/10.24963/ijcai.2020/695>
- LZE15 → Liang, D., Zhan, M., & Ellis, D. P. (2015). Content-aware collaborative music recommendation using pre-trained neural networks. *Proceedings of the 16th International Society for Music Information Retrieval Conference (ISMIR)*, 295–301
- MCSS08 → Mahdavi, I., Cho, N., Shirazi, B., & Sahebjamnia, N. (2008). Designing evolving user profile in e-CRM with dynamic clustering of Web documents. *Data & Knowledge Engineering*, 65(2), 355–372. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.datak.2007.12.003>
- MGA+15 → Mehrpoor, M., Gulla, J. A., Ahlers, D., Kristensen, K., Ghodrati, S., et al. (2015). Using process ontologies to contextualize recommender systems in engineering projects for knowledge access improvement. *Proceedings of the 16th European Conference on Knowledge Management (ECKM)*, 524–531. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15228053.2017.1313557>
- MIM10 → Marin, L., Isern, D., & Moreno, A. (2010). A generic user profile adaptation framework. In *Artificial intelligence research and development* (pp. 143–152, Vol. 220). IOS Press. <https://doi.org/10.3233/978-1-60750-643-0-143>
- MIM13 → Marin, L., Isern, D., & Moreno, A. (2013). Dynamic adaptation of numerical attributes in a user profile. *Applied Intelligence*, 39(2), 421–437. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10489-012-0421-5>
- MMI14 → Marin, L., Moreno, A., & Isern, D. (2014). Automatic preference learning on numeric and multi-valued categorical attributes. *Knowledge-Based Systems*, 56, 201–215. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.knosys.2013.11.012>

- Mo97 → Moukas, A. (1997). User modeling in a multiagent evolving system. *Proceedings of the 6th International Conference on User Modeling (UM)*
- MVC14 → Menéndez, H. D., Vindel, R., & Camacho, D. (2014). Combining time series and clustering to extract gamer profile evolution. *Proceedings of the 6th International Conference on Computational Collective Intelligence (ICCCI)*, 262–271. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-11289-3_27
- Nau+19 → Naumov, M., Mudigere, D., Shi, H.-J. M., Huang, J., Sundaraman, N., et al. (2019). Deep learning recommendation model for personalization and recommendation systems. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3394486.3403059>
- OLEKC18 → Obeid, C., Lahoud, I., El Khoury, H., & Champin, P.-A. (2018). Ontology-based recommender system in higher education. *Proceedings of the The Web Conference (WWW)*, 1031–1034. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3184558.3191533>
- OQP+16 → On-At, S., Quirin, A., Péninou, A., Baptiste-Jessel, N., Canut, M.-F., et al. (2016). Taking into account the evolution of users social profile: Experiments on Twitter and some learned lessons. *Proceedings of the 10th IEEE International Conference on Research Challenges in Information Science (RCIS)*. <https://doi.org/10.1109/rcis.2016.7549325>
- PBD23 → Purificato, E., Boratto, L., & De Luca, E. W. (2023). Leveraging graph neural networks for user profiling: Recent advances and open challenges. *Proceedings of the 32nd ACM international conference on information and knowledge management*, 5216–5219. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3583780.3615292>
- Pro+25 → Prottasha, N. J., Kowsher, M., Raman, H., Anny, I. J., Bhat, P., et al. (2025). User profile with large language models: Construction, updating, and benchmarking. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-024-75599-4>
- Puk14 → Pukkhem, N. (2014). LORecommendNet: An ontology-based representation of learning object recommendation. *Proceedings of the 10th International Conference on Computing and Information Technology (IC2IT)*, 293–303. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-06538-0_29
- Qi+20 → Qi, T., Wu, F., Wu, C., Huang, Y., & Xie, X. (2020). Privacy-preserving news recommendation model learning. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2003.09592*. <https://doi.org/10.18653/v1/2020.findings-emnlp.128>
- Qi+22 → Qi, T., Wu, F., Wu, C., & Huang, Y. (2022). News recommendation with candidate-aware user modeling. *Proceedings of the 45th international ACM SIGIR conference on research and development in information retrieval*, 1917–1921. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3477495.3531778>
- Qia+25 → Qiang, M., Wang, Z., Li, S., & Zhou, G. (2025). Exploring unified training framework for multimodal user profiling. *Proceedings of the 31st International Conference on Computational Linguistics*, 1699–1710
- RAPR23 → Fermé, E., Garapa, M., Reis, M. D., Almeida, Y., Paulino, T., et al. (2024). Knowledge-driven profile dynamics. *Artificial Intelligence*, 331, 1–30, article no.: 104117. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.artint.2024.104117>
- RDS+21 → Ravi, L., Devarajan, M., Sangaiyah, A. K., Wang, L., & Subramaniaswamy,

- V. (2021). An intelligent location recommender system utilising multi-agent induced cognitive behavioural model. *Enterprise Information Systems*, 15(10), 1376–1394. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17517575.2020.1812003>
- RHS+13 → Ruotsalo, T., Haav, K., Stoyanov, A., Roche, S., Fani, E., et al. (2013). SMARTMUSEUM: A mobile recommender system for the Web of Data. *Journal of Web Semantics*, 20, 50–67. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3199062>
 - RJ14 → Rana, C., & Jain, S. K. (2014a). An evolutionary clustering algorithm based on temporal features for dynamic recommender systems. *Swarm and Evolutionary Computation*, 14, 21–30. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.swevo.2013.08.003>
 - RJ14 pt 2 → Rana, C., & Jain, S. K. (2014b). An extended evolutionary clustering algorithm for an adaptive recommender system. *Social Network Analysis and Mining*, 4(1), 1–13, article no.: 164. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13278-014-0164-x>
 - RJ15 → Rana, C., & Jain, S. K. (2015). A study of the dynamic features of recommender systems. *Artificial Intelligence Review*, 43(1), 141–153. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10462-012-9359-6>
 - RL08 → Razmerita, L., & Lytras, M. D. (2008). Ontology-based user modelling personalization: Analyzing the requirements of a semantic learning portal. *Proceedings of the 1st World Summit on the Knowledge Society (WSKS)*, 354–363. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-540-87781-3_39
 - SA19 → Samin, H., & Azim, T. (2019). Knowledge based recommender system for academia using machine learning: A case study on higher education landscape of pakistan. *IEEE Access*, 7, 67081–67093. <https://doi.org/10.1109/access.2019.2912012>
 - SCP12 → Subramaniaswamy, V., & Chenthur Pandian, S. (2012). Effective tag recommendation system based on topic ontology using Wikipedia and WordNet. *International Journal of Intelligent Systems*, 27(12), 1034–1048. <https://doi.org/10.1002/int.21560>
 - SDD08 → Sutterer, M., Droegehorn, O., & David, K. (2008). User profile selection by means of ontology reasoning. *Proceedings of the 4th Advanced International Conference on Telecommunications (AICT)*, 299–304. <https://doi.org/10.1109/aict.2008.47>
 - Sil+23 → da Silva, F. L., Slodkowski, B. K., da Silva, K. K. A., & Cazella, S. C. (2023). A systematic literature review on educational recommender systems for teaching and learning: Research trends, limitations and opportunities. *Education and information technologies*, 28(3), 3289–3328. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10639-022-11341-9>
 - SMBZ24 → Salemi, A., Mysore, S., Bendersky, M., & Zamani, H. (2024). LaMP: When large language models meet personalization. <https://doi.org/10.18653/v1/2024.acl-long.399>
 - SMG06 → Schaefer, R., Mueller, W., & Groppe, J. (2006). Profile processing and evolution for smart environments. *Proceedings of the 3rd International Conference on Ubiquitous Intelligence and Computing (UIC)*, 746–755. https://doi.org/10.1007/11833529_76
 - SMLM25 → Sabouri, M., Mansoury, M., Lin, K., & Mobasher, B. (2025). Towards explainable temporal user profiling with LLMs. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3631700.3664869>
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